

ISic1556

I.Sicily inscription 1556

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

funerary

Material

marble

Object**Editor**

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

Jonathan Prag,James Cummings,James Chartrand,Valeria Vitale,Michael Metcalfe,Simona Stoyanova,Valentina Mignosa

Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Lilybaeum

Place of origin (modern)

Marsala

Provenance**Coordinates****Current Location**

Italy, Sicily, Palermo, Museo Archeologico

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

1. Ἰάσων Ἀρταφᾶντος
2. ἔζησεν ἀμέμπτω
3. (vac. undefined)ς ἔτη ο
4. Θεουδώρα
5. ἔζησεν ἀμέμπτω
6. (vac. undefined)ς ἔτη ζ

Apparatus

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 284799

EDR 105650

EDCS 41300030

PHI 175621

Bibliography

1923-. Supplementum epigraphicum graecum. *Supplementum epigraphicum graecum*. At 26.1077

undefined, undefined 1888-. Bulletin épigraphique. *Bulletin épigraphique*. At 1976.0058

Manni Piraino, M.T. 1973. Iscrizioni greche lapidarie del Museo di Palermo. *Sikelika* 6. Palermo. At 26

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